

TO INVOLVE PASSIVE STUDENTS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Xayrullayeva Zebuniso Alisherovna

Student of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Scientific adviser: **Burxanova Ma'mura Gulyamovna**

E-Mail: zebunisoXayrullayeva2001@gmail.com

Abstract: This article discusses strategies for teaching foreign languages and how to deal with pupils who have low competence rates.

Key words: English language, current innovative technologies, foreign language, teacher, teaching methodology.

In order to produce excellent results and contribute to the growth of the nation, we must acquire information and skills in accordance with the demands of the modern world and put them to use in practice. We require focus, effort, and, of course, a desire to learn new things. The quality of education and the effectiveness of students' learning have improved as a result of the reforms implemented in our nation's educational system. Because, according to our wise people, "Knowledge obtained in childhood is like a pattern carved on stone." The success of our young people in international science and knowledge competitions shows that the development work being done is on the rise correct path. Today, it is especially important to teach children other languages more thoroughly.

In accordance with the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan's Decision No. PQ-5117 of May 19, 2021, "On Measures to Bring the Activities of Popularization of Learning Foreign Languages to a Qualitatively New Level in the Republic of Uzbekistan," in chronological order The Cabinet of Ministers determines the following in order to successfully execute organizational measures to promote learning: The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan's Resolution No. PQ-5117, dated May 19, 2021, "On Measures to Bring the Activity of Popularizing the Study of Foreign Languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a Qualitatively New Level".

In accordance with paragraph 2, the Agency and its representatives are the State University of World Languages of Uzbekistan's 34 state units of the republican scientific-practical center for the development of novel approaches to teaching foreign languages, the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education and Public Education The fact that the system was created at the expense of 39 state units should be considered as knowledge. The agency's primary responsibilities will be to:

- promote the study of foreign languages among the populace and establish the conditions for perfect mastery;

- coordinate the introduction of internationally acclaimed textbooks and programs for teaching foreign languages at all levels of education; and - promote the development of modern teaching techniques in teachers;

- planning the teaching of highly sought-after foreign languages in light of the analyses' findings of the demands for experts who have mastered from various locations, industries, and educational institutions a second language;

- to create language learning strategies and guidelines that are appropriate for all levels of learners people in the field of teaching foreign languages in order to implement a chain of continuous education based on the premise of "kindergarten school-higher education organization-enterprise" coordination; significant duties on the implementation of numerous more measures are also presented. The choice makes clear how important the educational system is. Based on this, we can state that the majority of students' learning levels and all linguistic the teacher determines the interest of the students and their learning. "Why is the instructor playing a key part in students' education?" – is a reasonable inquiry. This is because, in the contemporary modern era, any knowledge to master a specific skill using free resources on the internet. But "Learning is not boring," despite textbooks. As they say, children learn in our nation from kindergarten through the school year as a result of the teacher's positive pressure, and as a result, the population gains the ability to "self study" in English. It is a little challenging to create and apply. Following is we can infer from this that the process of learning a language in our nation is largely dependent on the teacher, or rather, his expertise and experience, the ease and interest with which he can impart this knowledge to the student, as well as the use of contemporary technologies to further spark an interest in language learning. and is subject to how the methodology is applied.

Taking into account that most language students are specifically, kindergarteners or students, as everyone is aware, are more it takes a lot of expertise from the teacher to engage students in playful behavior, and schoolchildren are no different. Include all pupils, even teenagers, in the educational process. For instance, to spark their interest in learning other languages, the teacher engages kids in activities tailored to their preferences and uses fairy tales to evoke the culture of the language's native land. Children also pretend to be cartoon or fairytale characters and attempt to speak that language, and they believe themselves to be cartoon or fairytale characters. They will probably become interested in the language as a result. The instructor must be knowledgeable in more than just modern culture in order to make the courses engaging and pique the students' interest in the language methodologies, but also cutting-edge technology in the present era. Reading, writing, hearing, and speaking are the four

components that make up foreign language science, and each of them is broken down into distinct concepts and abilities. Modern information technologies are effectively used in the educational process through educational technology. By incorporating cutting-edge technologies into the educational process, it also aims to improve the effectiveness and quality of instruction. Utilizing such information and communication technology in particular has a number of benefits for learning a foreign language. Modern technology's function in language learning. Moreover, education is immeasurable. Every facet of learning a foreign language benefits from the use of technology, according to (reading, writing, listening and speaking). For instance, this procedure obviously requires a computer, player, and CDs in order to listen and understand. One of the most crucial aspects of language learning is listening comprehension. The reader must also focus on the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammar standards, and use of terminology and its meanings. employing a foreign language for instruction and learning. One of the most effective methods is using new technologies. Included in this procedure are:

- students can watch and listen to foreign language video clips, demonstrations, dialogues, movies, or cartoons using computers; - you can watch and listen to foreign language radio programs;

- the more conventional technique of using tape recorders and cassettes;

- the usage of CD players. For students, learning a foreign language is more engaging and effective when these technical tools are used. Interactive gaming as a teaching tool is becoming customary in classrooms today. It is well known that the class is built around a variety of games, which enables pupils to show off their skills, focus, advance their knowledge and abilities, and build strength. The activity that engages and accelerates the student forms the cornerstone of the usage of gaming technology. Psychologists claim that the psychological underpinnings of playful activities depend on a person's basic needs to express himself, find a secure place in life, exercise self-control, and reach his potential. Any game should be built around well acknowledged educational concepts and strategies. The themes of educational games should be related to those subjects. As it happens the learner works freely and is more engaged in this activity than they would be in a typical class because of games. It should be mentioned that the game is primarily a teaching tool. Students actively engage in game lessons, compete to win, and the teacher also educates the student through them. While playing English-language games, the student feels that he can speak, listen, understand, and write. As a result, the teacher designs unique games for every subject.

In conclusion, it should be noted that practically all famous historical personalities have acknowledged the mentors who influenced them in their

autobiographies. Because of this, the sources say that they reached numerous milestones. Many well-known adults and young people who have had great success are still around today. Despite their young, they advocate that everyone should have a mentor, regardless of their career or life path. The explanation is fairly straightforward: the instructor instructs, directs, identifies errors, and offers guidance. Therefore, it becomes challenging for students to identify when and where they made a mistake, why they made a mistake, and how to avoid repeat it if there is no teacher present during the process of learning a foreign language. Additionally, as previously said, the learner learns more responsible due to the teacher's scrutiny of his study, memorization of foreign words, and fitness regimen. As a result, the instructor is crucial to learning foreign languages as well as to every other subject and component of education.

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